

Investigation the Effect of Different Wire Material and Wire Diameter on MRR, SR and CV during WEDM Process for various Aluminum Metal Matrix Composite Materials

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Abstract

In this paper effect of wire electrode material and wire diameter on wire electrical discharge machining performance of Al+SiC, Al+B₄C, Al+ZrO₂ is reported. Uncoated copper, brass and molybdenum with different diameter of 0.2, 0.25, and 0.3mm is used. L₂₇ orthogonal array has been selected for experiment and analysis of variance is carried out on the basis of signal to noise ratio to find out which parameter most significant for material removal rate, surface roughness and cutting velocity. It was found that wire diameter, wire material and pulse on time is most significant parameter for material removal rate and cutting velocity whereas pulse off time is most significant parameter for surface roughness of Al+SiC, Al+B₄C, Al+ZrO₂ materials.

Keywords: Wire electrical discharge machining, Material removal rate, Surface roughness, Cutting velocity, Analysis of variance, Signal to noise ratio.

Nomenclature:

W_m	Wire material
W_d	Wire diameter (mm)
T_{on}	Pulse on time
$(\mu s) T_{off}$	Pulse off time
$(\mu s) I_p$	Peak current (amp)
W_t	Wire tension (kgf)
W_f	Wire feed rate (mm/min)
MRR	Material removal rate (mm ³ /min)
SR	Surface roughness (μm)
CV	Cutting velocity (mm/min)
Cu	Copper

B Brass

Mo Molybdenum

Introduction

Wire EDM is basically same as the vertical EDM process. In wire EDM, the conductive materials are machined with a series of electrical discharges (sparks) that are produced between an accurately positioned moving wire (the electrode) and the work piece. High frequency pulses of alternating or direct current are discharged from the wire to the work piece with a very small spark gap through an insulated dielectric fluid. Fluid is continuously flowing in the machining zone. Kanlayasiri and Boonmung (2007) studied WEDM process for DC53 die steel material and find out which machining parameter effects on the surface roughness. Analysis of variance technique was used to find out which variables affecting the surface roughness. It was found that pulse on time and peak current were most significant parameter for the surface roughness. Prasad (2008) describe mathematical model for the material removal rate and surface roughness in terms of the input variable for AISI D3 as a work material and brass wire as tool using the response surface methodology. Non sorting genetic algorithm use to find pareto optimal set of solution. Yang and Tzeng (2011) use the combine approach of taguchi's design method, response surface methodology, back propagation neural network and simulated annealing algorithm on WEDM processes. Analysis of variance use to find out which parameter are most significant factors for the WEDM process. It was also found that the percentage errors for MRR, R_a , and CD via a trained BPNN are less than which is measured from regression models derived by the RSM approach. Pulse on time is the most significant parameter for the MRR, SR and CD. Boopathi and Kumar (2012) describe dry wire electrical discharge machining process and experiments were conducted using the molybdenum wire as tool. During experiment consider five process parameters gap voltage, pulse on time, pulse off time, air mist pressure and discharge current each at five level for obtaining the a good surface finish and material removal rate. It was found that pulse-on time, discharge current and gap voltage are the most significant parameters in order to increase the metal-cutting speed and improve surface finish of dry WEDM. Also it was found that while increasing the air-mist pressure upto 5 bar MRR and surface finish values are improved. Further increasing the air-mist pressure, the MRR and surface finish values are reduced due to the high velocity of air-mist in the cutting zone. Khan and Rajput (2012) develop

a predictive model which gives the functional relationship between input and output parameter of WEDM for alloy steel. Artificial neural networks multiobjective optimization is used for modelling the wire electrical discharge machining process. It was found that surface quality of alloy steel material decreases as cutting speed increases. Rao and Krishna (2013) use a combined approach of principal component analysis coupled with Taguchi's robust theory for simultaneous optimization of correlated multiple responses of wire electrical discharge machining process for machining SiC_p reinforced ZC63 metal matrix composites material. Experiments were conducted by varying the particulate size, volume fraction, pulse-on time, pulse-off time and wire tension. Multiresponse optimization technique principal component analysis is used to derive the composite principal component which acts as the overall quality index in the process.

In present study effect of three different wire material with different diameter combinations on response characteristics like material removal rate, surface roughness, and cutting velocity during WEDM process have been studied. The optimal combination of input parameters has been determined for MRR, SR and CV. Most significant parameter for each case has also been determined. From the main effect plot for S/N ratios, it has been concluded that MRR and CV varies proportionally to pulse on time, wire diameter and wire material whereas SR varies proportionally to pulse off time.

Novelty of this paper to study effect of wire diameter and wire material on performance of Al+SiC, Al+B₄C, Al+ZrO₂ materials for material removal rate, cutting velocity and surface roughness. Uncoated copper, brass and molybdenum wire of different diameter 0.2, 0.25, 0.3 mm were utilized to conduct research.

Experiment Plan and Procedure

Experiments were conducted on the ELPULS-40DLX WEDM machine from Electronica India Pvt Ltd Pune shown in figure 1. Aluminum based metal matrix composite made by stir casting process were used as the work pieces. Three different material copper brass and molybdenum wire having different diameter of 0.20, 0.25, and 0.30 mm was used as the cutting tool. These seven input parameters namely wire material, pulse-on time (T_{on}), pulse-off time (T_{off}), wire diameter (W_d), peak current (I_p), wire feed rate (W_F) and wire tension (W_T) were chosen as variables to study their effect on the quality of cut in SiC_p/6061 aluminum, B₄C_p/6061 aluminum, ZrO₂ /6061 aluminum MMC. Parameter ranges and their level shown in Table 1. The response parameter in the present study was MRR, SR and CV. The experimental study was

carried out based on L_{27} orthogonal array and material removal rate and cutting velocity value was calculated using equation 1 and equation 2 respectively whereas surface roughness values were measured with surface tester.

$$MRR = \frac{W_b - W_a}{\rho \times T} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Cutting Velocity} = \frac{\text{Cutting length of workpiece}}{\text{meto cut}} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: WEDM Machine

Setup Table 1: Level of Selected Factors

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Factor	Units	Level1	Level2	Level3
W_m	--	Cu	B	Mo
W_d	mm	0.2	0.25	0.3
T_{on}	μs	108	118	128
T_{off}	μs	50	55	60
I_p	amp	100	150	200
W_t	kgf	4	7	10
W_f	m/min	3	6	9

Table 2: Material Removal Rate and S/N ratio for Al+SiC, Al+B₄C, Al+ZrO₂ Materials

Ex. No	W_m	W_d	T_{on}	T_{off}	I_p	W_t	W_f	MRR			S/N ratios		
								Al+SiC	Al+B ₄ C	Al+ZrO ₂	Al+SiC	Al+B ₄ C	Al+ZrO ₂
1	Cu	0.2	108	50	100	4	3	15.49	60.28	57.52	23.8	35.6	35.2
2	Cu	0.2	108	50	150	7	6	15.03	55.85	53.03	23.54	34.94	34.49
3	Cu	0.2	108	50	200	10	9	14.36	53.05	48.08	23.14	34.49	33.64
4	Cu	0.25	118	55	100	4	3	24.14	89.2	85.82	27.65	39.01	38.67
5	Cu	0.25	118	55	150	7	6	22.53	80.87	73.95	27.06	38.16	37.38
6	Cu	0.25	118	55	200	10	9	25.72	79.5	69.54	28.21	38.01	36.84

7	Cu	0.3	128	60	100	4	3	34.73	124.5	110.94	30.81	41.9	40.9
8	Cu	0.3	128	60	150	7	6	36.74	120.87	108.79	31.3	41.65	40.73
9	Cu	0.3	128	60	200	10	9	36.77	115.15	107.35	31.31	41.23	40.62
10	B	0.2	118	60	100	7	9	20.6	69.83	69.21	26.28	36.88	36.8
11	B	0.2	118	60	150	10	3	21.93	67.09	64.67	26.82	36.53	36.21
12	B	0.2	118	60	200	4	6	23.52	65.17	63.51	27.43	36.28	36.06
13	B	0.25	128	50	100	7	9	35.11	112.67	110.70	30.91	41.04	40.88
14	B	0.25	128	50	150	10	3	33.22	106.17	103.88	30.43	40.52	40.33
15	B	0.25	128	50	200	4	6	30.54	110.67	102.44	29.7	40.88	40.21
16	B	0.3	108	55	100	7	9	17.18	78.86	77.03	24.7	37.94	37.73
17	B	0.3	108	55	150	10	3	18.47	75.45	74.67	25.33	37.55	37.46
18	B	0.3	108	55	200	4	6	20.68	71.68	72.19	26.31	37.11	37.17
19	Mo	0.2	128	55	100	10	6	23.24	87.6	84.65	27.32	38.85	38.55
20	Mo	0.2	128	55	150	4	9	25.24	92.47	83.21	28.04	39.32	38.4
21	Mo	0.2	128	55	200	7	3	22.98	77.12	80.92	27.23	37.74	38.16
22	Mo	0.25	108	60	100	10	6	15.37	60.68	66.25	23.73	35.66	36.42
23	Mo	0.25	108	60	150	4	9	16.16	65.62	65.48	24.17	36.34	36.32
24	Mo	0.25	108	60	200	7	3	14.83	60.63	60.82	23.42	35.65	35.68
25	Mo	0.3	118	50	100	10	6	29.93	110.15	96.77	29.52	40.84	39.71
26	Mo	0.3	118	50	150	4	9	30.95	105.16	94.34	29.81	40.44	39.49
27	Mo	0.3	118	50	200	7	3	31.48	102.73	92.22	29.96	40.23	39.3

Table3:SurfaceRoughnessandS/Nratiofor Al+SiC,Al+B₄C,Al+ZrO₂Materials

Ex. No	W _m	W _d	T _{on}	T _{off}	I _p	W _t	W _f	SR			S/Nratios		
								Al+SiC	Al+B ₄ C	Al+ZrO ₂	Al+SiC	Al+B ₄ C	Al+ZrO ₂
1	Cu	0.2	108	50	100	4	3	3.067	3.094	3.078	-9.73	-9.81	-9.77
2	Cu	0.2	108	50	150	7	6	2.864	2.978	2.909	-9.14	-9.48	-9.27
3	Cu	0.2	108	50	200	10	9	2.812	2.983	2.88	-8.98	-9.49	-9.19
4	Cu	0.25	118	55	100	4	3	4.657	4.061	4.118	-13.36	-12.17	-12.29
5	Cu	0.25	118	55	150	7	6	4.283	4.049	4.069	-12.63	-12.15	-12.19
6	Cu	0.25	118	55	200	10	9	3.949	3.988	3.964	-11.93	-12.02	-11.96
7	Cu	0.3	128	60	100	4	3	5.015	4.443	4.486	-14.01	-12.95	-13.04
8	Cu	0.3	128	60	150	7	6	4.218	4.252	4.231	-12.5	-12.57	-12.53
9	Cu	0.3	128	60	200	10	9	4.187	4.274	4.221	-12.44	-12.62	-12.51
10	B	0.2	118	60	100	7	9	4.613	3.649	3.777	-13.28	-11.24	-11.54
11	B	0.2	118	60	150	10	3	4.087	3.574	3.641	-12.23	-11.06	-11.22
12	B	0.2	118	60	200	4	6	4.371	4.034	4.056	-12.81	-12.11	-12.16
13	B	0.25	128	50	100	7	9	4.457	4.289	4.269	-12.98	-12.65	-12.61
14	B	0.25	128	50	150	10	3	4.141	4.262	4.189	-12.34	-12.59	-12.44
15	B	0.25	128	50	200	4	6	4.775	4.682	4.557	-13.58	-13.41	-13.17
16	B	0.3	108	55	100	7	9	3.043	3.375	3.416	-9.67	-10.57	-10.67
17	B	0.3	108	55	150	10	3	3.996	3.484	3.491	-12.03	-10.84	-10.86

18	B	0.3	108	55	200	4	6	2.99	4.032	4.006	-9.51	-12.11	-12.05
19	Mo	0.2	128	55	100	10	6	3.378	3.427	3.397	-10.57	-10.7	-10.62
20	Mo	0.2	128	55	150	4	9	3.747	3.876	3.798	-11.47	-11.77	-11.59
21	Mo	0.2	128	55	200	7	3	3.944	4.099	4.006	-11.92	-12.25	-12.05
22	Mo	0.25	108	60	100	10	6	3.326	3.124	3.245	-10.44	-9.89	-10.22
23	Mo	0.25	108	60	150	4	9	3.507	3.422	3.473	-10.9	-10.69	-10.81
24	Mo	0.25	108	60	200	7	3	3.242	3.275	3.255	-10.22	-10.3	-10.25
25	Mo	0.3	118	50	100	10	6	4.027	4.009	4.02	-12.1	-12.06	-12.08
26	Mo	0.3	118	50	150	4	9	4.626	4.241	4.172	-13.3	-12.55	-12.41
27	Mo	0.3	118	50	200	7	3	4.459	4.333	4.228	-12.98	-12.74	-12.52

Table4:Cutting Velocity and S/N ratio for Al+SiC,Al+B₄C,Al+ZrO₂ Materials

Ex. No	W _m	W _d	T _{on}	T _{off}	I _p	W _t	W _f	CV			S/N ratios		
								Al+ SiC	Al+ B ₄ C	Al+ ZrO ₂	Al+ SiC	Al+ B ₄ C	Al+ ZrO ₂
1	Cu	0.2	108	50	100	4	3	3.234	3.51	3.72	10.19	10.91	11.41
2	Cu	0.2	108	50	150	7	6	3.29	3.54	3.73	10.34	10.98	11.43
3	Cu	0.2	108	50	200	10	9	3.04	3.34	3.57	9.66	10.47	11.05
4	Cu	0.25	118	55	100	4	3	5.12	4.26	4.36	14.19	12.59	12.79
5	Cu	0.25	118	55	150	7	6	4.949	4.57	4.58	13.89	13.2	13.22
6	Cu	0.25	118	55	200	10	9	4.235	4.32	4.39	12.54	12.71	12.85
7	Cu	0.3	128	60	100	4	3	3.63	3.97	4.23	11.2	11.98	12.53
8	Cu	0.3	128	60	150	7	6	4.48	4.6	4.69	13.03	13.26	13.42
9	Cu	0.3	128	60	200	10	9	3.425	3.79	4.08	10.69	11.57	12.21
10	B	0.2	118	60	100	7	9	5.072	3.92	3.82	14.1	11.87	11.64
11	B	0.2	118	60	150	10	3	4.336	4.09	3.9	12.74	12.23	11.82
12	B	0.2	118	60	200	4	6	4.008	3.83	3.71	12.06	11.66	11.39
13	B	0.25	128	50	100	7	9	6.972	6.97	6.97	16.87	16.86	16.86
14	B	0.25	128	50	150	10	3	7.16	6.93	6.9	17.1	16.81	16.78
15	B	0.25	128	50	200	4	6	6.986	6.94	6.91	16.88	16.83	16.79
16	B	0.3	108	55	100	7	9	1.819	3.05	3.22	5.2	9.69	10.16
17	B	0.3	108	55	150	10	3	1.745	2.95	3.11	4.84	9.4	9.86
18	B	0.3	108	55	200	4	6	1.811	3	3.14	5.16	9.54	9.94
19	Mo	0.2	128	55	100	10	6	2.14	4.38	4.71	6.61	12.83	13.46
20	Mo	0.2	128	55	150	4	9	3.235	4.37	4.69	10.2	12.81	13.42
21	Mo	0.2	128	55	200	7	3	3.714	4.16	4.51	11.4	12.38	13.08
22	Mo	0.25	108	60	100	10	6	1.498	1.73	1.91	3.51	4.76	5.62
23	Mo	0.25	108	60	150	4	9	1.633	1.83	1.98	4.26	5.25	5.93
24	Mo	0.25	108	60	200	7	3	1.549	1.73	1.87	3.8	4.76	5.44
25	Mo	0.3	118	50	100	10	6	5.961	5.95	5.95	15.51	15.49	15.49
26	Mo	0.3	118	50	150	4	9	6.118	5.91	5.92	15.73	15.43	15.45
27	Mo	0.3	118	50	200	7	3	5.217	5.35	5.46	14.35	14.57	14.74

Results and Discussion

Main effect plots have been plotted using mean of the signal to noise ratio for each parameter at all levels. Analysis of variance is performed and signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio is determined to know the level of significance of the process parameters. In ANOVA percent contribution (%P) is calculated which indicates the relative power of a factor to reduce variation. For a factor with a higher percent contribution, a small variation will have a great influence on the performance. The signal to noise (S/N) ratio provides a measure of the impact of noise factors on performance. The larger the S/N ratio, the more robust the product is against noise. The equations for calculating S/N ratios for smaller the better (SB), larger the better (LB) type characteristics are respectively as follows

$$S/N_{sb} = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^n y_i^2 \right) \quad (3)$$

$$S/N_{lb} = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{r} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{y_i} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where r = number of replications, y_i = measured value of the output variable. In the present study we have used the equation for calculating S/N ratio larger the better for material removal rate, cutting velocity and smaller the better for surface roughness.

(b)

(c)

Figure2:Signaltonoiseratio
maineffectplotof(a)Al+SiC,(b)Al+B4C(c)Al+ZrO2materialformaterialremoval rate

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure3:Signaltonoiseratio
maineffectplotof(a)Al+SiC,(b)Al+B₄C(c)Al+ZrO₂materialforsurfaceroughness

(a)

Figure4:Signaltonoiseratio
 maineffectplotof(a)Al+SiC,(b)Al+B₄C(c)Al+ZrO₂materialforsurfaceroughness

Table5:Optimumconditionand%contributionofeachParameterforMaterialRemovalrate,Surface
 Roughness, CuttingVelocityof all threematerials

Output Parameter	Input Parameter	Workpiece Material					
		Al+SiC		Al+B ₄ C		Al+ZrO ₂	
		Optimum Condition	% Contribution	Optimum Condition	% Contribution	Optimum Condition	% Contribution
MRR	W _m	B	0.99	Mo	0.233	B	0.333
	W _d	0.3	21.969	0.3	33.976	0.3	32.357
	T _{on}	128	69.44	128	59.436	128	61.939
	T _{off}	50	5.133	50	3.521	50	2.124
	I _p	200	0.123	100	1.517	100	2.354
	W _t	4	0.098	4	0.413	4	0.234
	W _f	9	0.116	9	0.048	3	0.062

SR	W_m	Mo	2.636	Mo	2.506	Mo	3.507
	W_d	0.2	8.885	0.25	21.568	0.2	23.366
	T_{on}	108	65.238	108	61.529	108	61.056
	T_{off}	55	3.477	60	0.618	50	0.014
	I_p	200	0.449	200	4.725	100	2.131
	W_t	10	150.18	10	6.925	10	7.089
	W_f	6	3.109	9	0.313	9	0.347
CV	W_m	Cu	5.415	B	4.953	B	2.966
	W_d	0.25	4.792	0.3	1.996	0.3	1.757
	T_{on}	118	52.843	128	53.052	128	53.973
	T_{off}	50	32.596	50	38.637	50	31.821
	I_p	150	0.607	150	0.555	150	0.392
	W_t	7	0.879	7	0.018	7	0.02
	W_f	3	0.025	6	0.266	6	0.176

Figure 2 (a-c) shows the main effective plots for signal to noise ratio calculated for material removal rates obtained for different work piece materials. It can be seen that material removal rate is observed to be increasing with increasing wire diameter and pulse on time. Because increasing the pulse on time and wire diameter the energy supplied and spark occur to the working gap is increase so more materials remove from the work piece surface. In order to identify the significant factors which affect material removal rates for different work piece material analysis of variance has been carried out for all three work piece which is shown in Table 5. Percentage contribution of the factors pulse on time and wire diameter has the highest contribution among all the factors considered. Thus it can be concluded that pulse on time and wire diameter has statistically the most significant effect on material removal rate.

Figure 3 (a-c) shows the main effective plots for signal to noise ratio calculated for surface roughness obtained for different work piece materials. It can be seen pulse on time, wire diameter and wire tension is most effective parameter for surface roughness because as we increase pulse on time energy per spark also get increase so material removed per spark is increase so more size of crater is created by each single spark so surface roughness is increase with pulse on time. On other side when pulse off time increase there is more time to remove the melted material by sparks so surface roughness is decrease and quality of surface is improved.

Another most effective parameter is wire tension when wire tension increase surface roughness decreases it is due to with high tension on wire it less than with low tension so it gives smooth surface by machining. Analysis of variance has been carried out for all three work piece material which is shown in Table 5 to identify the effective factors that affect surface roughness. It can be clearly observed that percentage contribution of the factors pulse on time, wire diameter and wire tension has the highest contribution among all the factors considered respectively. Thus it can be concluded that pulse on time, wire diameter and wire tension has statistically the most significant effect on surface roughness.

Figure 4(a-c) shows the signal to noise ratio analysis for cutting velocity. Pulse on time, pulse off time, wire diameter, and wire material is most effective parameter for cutting velocity. As pulse on time increase energy per spark is increase so material is cut faster and increase cutting velocity. But during pulse off time there is no any material get removed so wire is not moving so cutting velocity is decrease. Wire material and wire diameter effect on electrical resistance of wire and electrical resistance effect on intensity of energy imparted during spark. Analysis of variance has been carried out for all three work piece material which is shown in Table

5 to identify the effective factors that affect cutting velocity. It can be clearly observed that percentage contribution of the factors pulse on time, pulse off time, wire material and wire diameter has the highest contribution among all the factors considered respectively. Thus it can be concluded that pulse on time, pulse off time, wire material and wire diameter has statistically the most significant effect on cutting velocity.

Conclusion

- For higher material removal rate of aluminum silicon carbide, aluminum boron carbide and aluminum zirconium oxide material pulse on time is 128 μ s; wire diameter 0.3 and brass wire material is best for aluminum silicon carbide and aluminum zirconium oxide whereas for aluminum boron carbide copper wire electrode is best.
- For better surface finish of aluminum silicon carbide, aluminum boron carbide and aluminum zirconium oxide material low value of pulse on time 108 μ s and molybdenum wire electrode is significant parameter for all material where as 0.2mm wire diameter is suitable for aluminum silicon carbide, aluminum zirconium oxide and

0.25mm wire diameter is suitable for aluminum boron carbide for achieving better surface finish of all three work material.

- For achieving higher cutting velocity of aluminum silicon carbide material pulse on time 118 μ s wire diameter 0.25mm and wire material copper is best. Whereas for aluminum boron carbide and aluminum zirconium oxide material pulse on time 128 μ s wire diameter 0.3mm and wire material brass is best.

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